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Geometric proof for reimann zeta function hypothesis 0.5 $\Rightarrow 180^\circ \Rightarrow \pi$

Pre requisite

The theory linking geometry and algebraic proofs. I can show this but it will be in a category of math commonly known as math lore . For this geometry and presiding discovery it unravels how math domains , symbolic notations (+ \Rightarrow) interlink in math as a computational language.

Disclaimer

The proof by geometry is a proof enough just as proof by counter proof is acceptable in discreet math. The solution i have and surrounding theory and conjectures are heavily in discreet math and group theory

Where to find the geometry proof online .

- lishi.onrender.com
- <https://www.geogebra.org/classic/y9xmzqnv>
- <https://www.geogebra.org/m/ejxmemak>.
- <https://t.me/+f6ysCsYrpRAwZDI8>

Note the proof has been online in the public domain on telegram channel
<https://t.me/+Huv58-fv3PU5Mjk0>

. The ensuing conversation is on scientific publication vs self publishing. At the moment i would consider tg to be a public facing publishing platform same as any scientific journal but the rules and definition of what public is remains gray areas.

For any questions or peer review feedback

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